

CONTINUOUS SPIRITUAL EDUCATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF PREPARATION FOR THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation: In this article, opinions on increasing the activity of introducing educational standards based on a new approach to the training of future physical education teachers, on awakening a sense of responsibility for the chosen profession, on the development of various reforms in society are presented.

Key words and phrases: socio-economic, independent education, modern outlook, social necessity, continuous education, physical education teachers, innovative and digital, educational standards, Education and training, scientific-methodical.

– It is an important task of the time to pay attention to future specialists studying in higher educational institutions, who have thorough professional training and become skilled masters of their profession based on the requirements of the present time. The more knowledgeable and skillful educators are, the more knowledgeable and well-rounded people they can educate the future generation. Future pedagogues need to know what kind of material and technical base the educational institution has, how many children are educated there, what kind of pedagogical team it is, what kind of educational tasks it solves. Documents such as reports, journals, and the child's personal sheet can be of great help to the student. Future pedagogues try to collect as much information as possible about their students, observe the work of pedagogues with their help, and with the help of methodists of pedagogical institutes, they perform the tasks of ideological, political, moral, intellectual, labor, aesthetic and physical education. taking into account plans its activities from the position of a complex approach.

– The reforms implemented in the education system in our country are based on the democratic education system, and the ideas promoted in it are as follows:

– 1) It is necessary to build a person's spiritual culture and spiritual upbringing on the basis of all the achievements of humanity in the current period;

- 2) It is necessary to achieve the priority of national and universal values in the formation of spiritual education;
- 3) In the formation of spiritual education, it is necessary to avoid elements that are far from nationalism and contrary to it.
- In Uzbekistan, the work on the scientific and technological reform of youth education on a modern basis calls for its formation based on scientifically based basic competencies and qualities based on today's needs.
- A new, systematic approach to education, in the guaranteed formation of basic qualities in a child, family, preschool education, general education, secondary special vocational and higher educational institutions, the social-pedagogical possibilities of neighborhoods should be fully revealed and among them requires raising the scientific-methodological integrity to a new level.
- Loyalty to the motherland, duty and responsibility, initiative and other qualities remain as theoretical concepts in the minds of young people, but do not become practical habits in their nature. As a result, there is a discrepancy between their words about these qualities and their actions, which creates a number of problems for young men and women who enter independent life every year to find their place in life.
- The lack of formation of high goals, self-mobilization to study, insufficient development of the qualities of will, perseverance, perseverance, and action in some students harms the quality of education.
- In the field of spiritual education, there are not enough educational materials, including methodological manuals for the field of spiritual education, necessary textbooks for students.
- In this regard, the further development of the system of spiritual education through the successful implementation of the concept of "Continuous spiritual education" is of particular importance.
- The purpose of the concept is to gradually form age-appropriate social skills and qualities necessary for an independent and happy life in the young generation.
- To achieve this goal, to implement it in practice, it is necessary to perform the following tasks:
 - development and implementation of the methodology of education, which starts from the period of pregnancy and lasts until adulthood, based on the principles of gradualism and continuity;

- effective use of advanced achievements of national and modern pedagogy in child education;
- to regularly improve the knowledge and skills of teachers along with students;
- establishing an effective cooperation mechanism between family, neighborhood and educational institutions, as well as mass media and other social structures in the formation of spiritual education;
- spiritual education is based on the principles of gradual development and continuity.
- System of continuous spiritual education:
 - state and non-state educational institutions implementing educational programs in accordance with state educational standards;
 - scientific-pedagogical institutions that carry out scientific-research works in the field of education;
 - introduced through state administration bodies, public organizations, neighborhood and family institutions.
- Nationalization of the educational system on the basis of the national educational institution;
- To be a basis for forming universal, national-spiritual values in the behavior and behavior of every member of society;
- To give a person a programmatic guide to deeply understand the essence of national and universal culture sources;
- To guide a person in the pursuit of world-scale socio-economic and cultural processes through cultural values.

In general, we can express the role of the process of continuous spiritual education in the training of future specialists by the following:

1. The process of continuous spiritual education shows how attractive this language is, due to the fact that each nation was created in its mother tongue. This develops a feeling of not being indifferent to one's mother tongue.
2. Continuous spiritual education reveals the identity of each nation. Because they were formed directly on the basis of the spirit of this nation.
3. Continuous spiritual education encourages every person to love the history of his people and homeland, to be proud of his ancestors at every moment.
4. Every specialist formed in the process of continuous spiritual education is encouraged to become skilled builders of the future, who cannot be covered by extraneous ideas.

In the process of professional work, it is necessary to implement the following features in their activities.

1. Clarity and stability of the teacher's political views and beliefs, real reputation in front of students.

2. To actively participate in the entire social life of the country and bring the acquired experience to educational institutions, to involve students in this activity, to ensure their active participation in social life.

3. To look with great interest in the personality of each student and to organize all team work.

4. Teachers should think about the future, not the demands of today.

5. To care about their relationship with children, their fate, to be interested in the future of their children.

6. To influence the personality of the student in every way.

7. In-depth study of the advanced pedagogical experience and the theory of education and upbringing, to understand all the innovations, to compare them with their own experience, to apply some of them in their work. [9]

The teacher's creativity awakens the student's creativity. They educate their students in the spirit of loyalty to the motherland and instill noble qualities in their hearts. Therefore, it is important to develop a system of personal activity in the professional skills of teachers. Life is a world of discoveries. Experience, style, opinions are diverse. As a result of effective work, it moves to the hearts of students through proofs and arguments. It affects their feelings. Students are the teacher's pride and future. Therefore, their intention is to see students in the ranks of independent country builders, engineers, devotees of science and enlightenment. The first goal of the teacher is to make his student literate as soon as possible. But its implementation is very difficult. A teacher's development of his own activity system and strict adherence to it is one of the important factors of his success in the field of education. The teacher should not be limited to teaching the same methods. On the contrary, it is necessary to work tirelessly on improving teaching methods. A teacher's interaction with students has a great influence on the results of education. Love for a child is never unrequited [10:79]

Etiquette is a moral category that expresses a certain quality of a particular person. Etiquette is a set of positive moral qualities that apply to an individual, nation, nation, nation. Man is the greatest gift of nature. He is endowed with such great qualities as intelligence, consciousness, insight, that a person polishes and develops these qualities and leads the world and mankind to perfection.

The level of development of a person as a person is determined by the degree to which the elements of manners, ethics, culture, and spirituality are embodied in him.

Etiquette shows the ability of each person to behave and communicate with the community. Morality is a set of norms of behavior accepted in society and approved by public opinion. A complex of all positive, intellectual achievements accumulated during the activity of culture-society and citizens living in it. Spirituality is a complex of all positive, intellectual qualities that reflect the human mind.

Achieving mental maturity is a step-by-step, gradual process of voluntary actions, continuous activity, self-sacrifice, thirst for knowledge.

Independent thinking begins with understanding, understanding, reasoning. Comprehension is to understand the essence of an idea. Observation is the logical interpretation of this idea.

Thinking is the selection and practical application of existing scientific and life knowledge in the human mind.

It is important to form the moral culture of students based on the directions listed above. Because, in this spiritual environment, the student performs his activities and realizes his identity. He communicates with his spiritual knowledge. Therefore, ensuring the effectiveness of forming the moral culture of students and young people depends on the spiritual environment

The moral culture of students, the effect of their spiritual actions is determined by the attitude of the teacher (leader) and the student towards their activities. That is why a teacher or a leader should study the stages of historical development of spiritual heritage, rely on them in practical activities, it is incomparable in forming the personality culture of a person. Such an approach requires creativity from the participants of the educational process, from teachers and students. A creative teacher (leader) widely and effectively uses the possibilities of spiritual values in forming the moral culture of young students. The success of forming the moral culture of students depends on the creativity of the teacher and the student. There are conditions characterizing this factor, which are: teacher's in-depth knowledge of general pedagogy and special specialization, professional skills, culture of friendly communication with students, level of spirituality and culture, effective form of education and It consists of the ability to choose methods, to be able to predict the result in advance, to be able to guide based on imagination and pedagogical discoveries, the breadth of interest, the study of the spiritual heritage of the environment in

the community of the higher educational institution. If the teacher pays attention to these factors, creativity will increase. These factors help him a lot in forming the culture of student youth. As a result of the teacher's creativity, students and young people get deep knowledge about the history, literature, art, traditions and customs of their ancestors. Students' interest in spiritual heritage increases. In the course of the lesson, a friendly, healthy spiritual environment is created, and as a result of the effective use of sources of spiritual heritage, the moral culture of students is perfected. The formation of the moral culture of students depends, firstly, on the success of the teaching process, and secondly, on the content of education and the activity of teacher-student cooperation. Cooperation requires creativity, responsibility, and activity. In this case: the teacher should be able to clearly see the goal of each lesson, correctly determine the tasks to be performed; Scientific, consistent and educational character of the content of the knowledge in the course of the lesson, interestingness increases the interest of the students in the knowledge learned from the educational and educational side. Expanding their knowledge builds skills and competencies such as high character. Of course, special attention is paid to the essence of the topic when choosing lesson forms. For example, in vocational colleges, the literature class is organized in the form of a traditional lesson or discussion, the methodology class can be organized in the form of a seminar or discussion, foreign language classes can be organized in the form of games or question-and-answer, conversation classes. It is important to use methods such as question-and-answer, controversial situations, independent work, and the use of various games in order to increase the effectiveness of the formation of students' moral culture in all forms of lesson processes. Teaching students about the past, literature, history, national customs and traditions in forming the spiritual qualities of students requires the teacher to always be active. Satisfying the student's spiritual needs and developing his interest is carried out through independent works, various creative works (essays, abstracts, etc.). Independent work is an integral part of the teacher's and student's activities. In independent and creative work, the student works on himself, is creatively searched, while forming his own point of view and views, he shows his worldview and spiritual level. Independent work requires more work on textbooks, analysis of the content of sources, preparation of lectures, abstracts, abstracts, writing creative essays (also in a foreign language), written answers to cards, drawing up various tables, diagrams, schemes. All this requires research. 4 different sources are used to organize independent work and seminars. 1. To textbook materials. 2.

Spiritual heritage, considered folklore, religious sources, classical literature, etc. 3. Mass media materials (magazines, newspapers, radio, broadcasts, global programs); 4. Life examples (family traditions, customs, paintings, spiritual values, etc.). Wide use of oral independent work types and some written independent work (essay, finding written answers to questions, filling in tables, diagrams, cards) in the form of a mixed lesson aimed at strengthening the essence of the studied topic in students' practical activities. gives a good result. The use of game situations in foreign language and literature lessons will be effective. For example, in literature classes, discussions and debates such as "Our guest of scholars", "Timuri artists", "Today's era - through the eyes of scholars" can be organized. In methodology lessons, it is very useful to organize exchanges of ideas among students about the ideas of Eastern scholars about education and their spiritual heritage. In the course of the lesson, the pedagogue should skillfully use the sources of spiritual heritage, take into account their educational and educational impact. , regardless of how the lesson is organized (game lesson, discussion lesson, test lesson, etc.), to be active, creative, decisive in organizing it, to know the spiritual heritage well and to be able to put it into practice It is necessary. Organizing non-traditional forms of lessons based on independent oral preparation of students is one of the effective methods of forming character and culture. It is possible to conduct discussion-discussion classes on various topics. In the process of preparing for such classes, students have access to a wide range of spiritual resources. , refers to works of art, samples of folklore, pandnoms, religious sources, scientific, popular, autobiographical works dedicated to the life of Eastern scholars, press and mass information materials. As a result, he finds answers to problematic questions and gets to know the spiritual heritage of his ancestors.

If such classes are organized on the basis of sufficient training, skills and extensive knowledge, experience, and independence, the following positive results will be obtained that shape the student's moral culture: during the class, the student's freedom, independence, and activity will be achieved; students learn to rely on the opinion of the team, to respect it, thereby developing a culture of mutual respect and communication; students acquire the skills of defending their opinions and views and conveying them to others; Students develop the ability to judge the views of one or another writer, the nature of problems raised on the basis of folk pedagogy, life experience, and the opportunity and basis of the environment; the level of knowledge of students about the spiritual lifestyle of the Uzbek people increases, their moral and

spiritual qualities are formed; every student has an increased sense of self-demand, self-control, attention to work on oneself and self-awareness. Such a successful result is shown in test lessons and final lessons.

The main criteria of student character culture are: humanity, hard work, national pride, patriotism, love, faith, creativity, activity, initiative, self-control and self-evaluation. This requirement is implemented through the attitude of the student to his duty to his country, parents, friends, community, activity and creativity characteristics manifested in the educational process. Controlling one's own knowledge, behavior, attitude to the environment, organization of self-evaluation is effectively manifested through the student's written creative activity. Effective forms of education include the tools and methods of traditional and non-traditional types of lessons, including various creative written works of students during the educational process

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